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Sustainable Transfer of a German PPBL Model to a Mongolian Environment: Intercultural Experiences, Reflections, & Recommendations

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ABSTRACT

In our increasingly connected and global society, it is necessary for students to have interdisciplinary and intercultural skills to work with people from all over the world, for successful knowledge transfer, and for life-long-learning and encouragement of collaborative skills. Since 1998, a German technical university developed and continually improves upon a project-oriented and problem-based learning (PPBL) model that integrates both teamwork and systems thinking (engineering design) into an intensive, immersive project week. This model was then transferred to a newly formed Mongolian university. At the beginning, German academic staff introduced the Mongolian faculty to the PPBL model and taught the course for two years. For full empowerment and transfer of procedural and informal knowledge of the PPBL model, Mongolian academic staff attended a week-long workshop to learn and adapt the German model. This past year, the course was taught by Mongolian staff with mentoring from the German faculty. Our current snapshot shows that the transfer of the German PPBL model to a Mongolian university is on the path to be successful. Based on our experiences, we propose a feedback style which focuses on positive reinforcement of team resources in social environments where participants are not used to constructive feedback.

Conference Key Areas: Continuing Engineering Education and Lifelong Learning; Sustainability in Engineering Education; Engineering Skills

Keywords: PPBL model; sustainable knowledge transfer; intercultural experiences; cultural adaptations

1 INTRODUCTION

As we are living in a progressively complex and globally connected world, there is an increased need for students with project skills (teamwork and system thinking) and knowledge transfer between individuals, disciplines, universities, cultures, and countries to further encourage collaborative skills and life-long learning.

Accelerating global change includes socio-economic, earth system, and technological developments such as “Industry 4.0” and “big data”¹⁻⁴. This has led to three major trends that impact and change the workplace: informatization, globalization, and financialization^{5,6}, which further lead to an informational capitalism with the specific characteristics of a “knowledge society”⁷⁻⁹.

As a result, work has become organized in a more temporal, network-like structure and more knowledge-intensive^{5,6}. Highly qualified workers should be creative, socially competent, and self-organized and be able to move easily between the “real” and virtual worlds along with knowing and efficiently using the related communication channels needed for these transitions¹⁰.

The increase of complexity and flexibility at the work space leads to a continuous entanglement of working (doing) and learning¹¹. Employees need to be proactive and

adaptable with twenty-first century skills to be successful within this setting¹² and requirements along with the ability and readiness for lifelong learning^{13,14}.

Along with these developments and trends in the workplace, learning in higher education focuses on the approaches of constructivism¹⁵ and connectivism^{16,17}. Therefore, learning environments should be designed that will prepare students fully for the future, an increasingly interconnected, global world and workplace. These learning environments typically combine learner-centered, knowledge-centered, assessment-centered, and community-centered aspects¹⁸, and goes hand in hand with a blurring of the separation between formal and informal learning¹⁹. These trends in higher education learning highlight and support “pervasive learning”²⁰ in “enabling learning environments”²¹.

Project-orientated learning and design courses enables concurrent teaching and learning of teamwork and systems thinking (application of design) skills in a structured learning environment that combines aspects of their future workplace. This allows students to witness and experience the “messiness” of real-life industrial and teamwork problems, and has been shown to have long-term, positive impact on teamwork skills²²⁻²⁶.

Drawing from this background, this paper discusses an innovative learning environment developed at a technical university in Germany and further describes the knowledge transfer of the concept to a Mongolian university. First, we will shortly introduce the project-oriented and problem-based learning (PPBL) model developed as an interdisciplinary, international project course. Next, we will report on and reflect upon our intercultural experience with our cooperation with a Mongolian university, and the shared learning experience of transferring the PPBL model as well as practical, informal knowledge to their academic staff.

2 GERMAN PPBL MODEL

The German PPBL model has been detailed previously²⁷⁻³². Shortly, this model was originally developed in 1998 in collaboration with the Center for Educational Development at the German university as a monodisciplinary intensive, immersive, one-week design project course for first year students in mechanical and process engineering. In 2011, the monodisciplinary course was expanded and transformed into an interdisciplinary course and in 2012 was further expanded into an international, interdisciplinary course with German and American engineering students.

The core tenant of the German PPBL model is the concurrent teaching of teamwork and design skills in an innovative learning environment where students apply these skills through practice and reflection. The task teams are given is designed to be open-ended, complex, challenging, and similar to a team-orientated industrial project, and this leads to each team having finite resources e.g. time and knowledge that they must manage throughout the week to develop a solution. To support and not overwhelm the students, a support system consists of the following elements was developed:

- Team advising. Team advisers are mostly students of sociology, psychology, and pedagogy who have been intensely trained by the Center for Educational Development in team building and team competences. They establish standards and criteria of behavior modeled by professional (industrial) teams emphasizing team working techniques, communication, and problem solving e.g., discussion, moderation, visualization, through self-reflection, team-reflection, team-feedback, and additional feedback from the team adviser. The team advisers co-advise teams tandemly with a technical adviser.

- Technical advising. Technical advisers are academic staff who follow the principle of minimum help³³ and the Socratic questioning method. This means empowering teams with as minimum help as possible but as much as needed or necessary. Technical advisers give mostly general strategic, problem solving, and design process advice along with motivation and content-specific advice as needed.
- Help desk. The help desk is a scientific research resource for teams and is also orientated by the principle of minimum help. It follows the motto of, “Good answers to good questions,” meaning teams need to have pre-formed questions for the help desk and not just ask for a solution and/or if they are correct or wrong about an idea.
- Experts. The teams have the opportunity during the middle of the project week to consult with outside experts, typically professors and/or industrial experts. Each interview is approximately 10-15 minutes so each team needs to be prepared for these consultations.
- Jury panel. At the end of the week, teams present their final solution to a jury panel of experts, professors, etc.
- Project leaders and supervision. The project leaders not only organize the project week, develop the task(s), train the team and technical advisers and help desk members but also supervise and provide technical and didactic support to all the staff during the project week as needed.

The positive, value-added impact of this PPBL model at the German university has previously been shown²⁷⁻³². Shortly, students are meeting the desired learning outcomes of the model including learning teamwork skills, disciplinary skills, and interdisciplinary integration along with increasing intrinsic motivation for their further studies.

3 TRANSFER OF PPBL MODEL – INTERNALIZATION OF STUDY PROJECTS

In 2014, the German PPBL model was expanded once more and brought to a Mongolian university. The model was transferred following a scaffolding procedure from introducing the Mongolian staff to the project to empowering them to identify, adapt, and make the model their own. The first step introduced them to the project and model with German staff traveling to Mongolia to lead the project week and perform the major roles. This was followed by Mongolian staff attending a workshop held at the German university to train them in the major aspects of the PPBL model, followed by mentoring the Mongolian staff during the following project week at their university. The last step will be for the Mongolian staff to continuously improve and implement the model for their needs.

3.1 Step 1 – Experiences in Mongolia

For two years, the German PPBL model was implemented with German academic staff maintaining the major roles, i.e., team and technical advisers, experts, and help desk, while the Mongolian academic staff had more supporting roles, i.e., organization at the university level and experts. Tasks similar in scope to German project courses were developed but adapted with relevance to Mongolian society, e.g., development of an autonomous robot that is capable of collecting and sorting litter alongside the road and removal of nitrogen oxides from diesel exhaust using urea. Due to the smaller size in comparison to the German project courses (two groups, each with approximately 10 students), the help desk and expert interviews were not utilized, but German staff were available to meet with groups as needed to discuss solutions and problems as they arose. Mongolian students were in their first semester of studies in mechanical engineering, environmental engineering, or raw materials and process engineering, but all three programs have the same curriculum for the first four semesters.

One major difference seen between the original German PPBL model and the one adapted is the role and the level of interaction of the technical adviser. In the German PPBL model, the principle of minimum help³³ guides the interactions of the technical adviser with it being a more passive role unless asked specific questions by the team and providing more strategic advice and motivation than subject-intensive advice. However, it was experienced that the project courses led by the German staff that the technical adviser needed to take on a more active role in the teams by providing subject assisted learning, direct information about design approach, and more general motivation.

There is a standard evaluation procedure developed for the underlying, core PPBL model which consists of three main parts. One part is the daily reflection with the student groups for their learning process. Another part is the daily review with the team and technical advisers and project leaders for the advisers' learning process and for learning adjustments that need to be made in the student groups. The third part is the final evaluation for improving the model for the next year(s). For the the first two Mongolian cohorts, there is only data for the 2014 cohort, but we do not have permission of students (small cohort of approximately 20 students) to publish. It was only gathered and used for internal use, e.g., improving the learning process (of students, advisers, and project leaders) and improving the model for future courses.

3.2 Step 2 – Workshop in Germany

After two years of leading the course at the Mongolian university by German staff, a training workshop was developed to fully transfer the PPBL model and enable the Mongolian university staff to learn and adapt the model. The workshop followed a constructivist approach with half of the day working directly with the trainers and the afternoons were for self-directed study where the content could be deepened by additional literature reading, guided reflection questions, and/or adapting and transferring the learned content to their own university. The learning outcomes from the workshop were as follows: The Mongolian university staff

- have received an overview of the organizational standard procedure of a project week,
- are empowered to qualify and implement the support system, mostly consisting of team and technical advisers,
- have practically applied the approach of constructive feedback as an intervention method at a team level as a team adviser and have practiced the steps involved in the principle of minimum help³³ as applied by technical advisers, and
- have reflected upon the concept and the connected challenges to generate ideas on how to adapt and sustainably implement the German PPBL model at their own university.

The workshop was broken down into five complementary building units.

- The first unit gave an overview of the German PPBL model including the concept, procedure, support system, and critical success factors regarding organization and didactic preparations for study projects grounded in the broader scope of project-orientated and problem-based learning.
- In the second unit, the participants learned about the didactic approach of team advising including goals, tasks, attitudes, settings, and competences of team advising as well as how to recruit and train team advisers. The method of constructive feedback as intervention was introduced, applied, and feed-backed by the trainers.
- Equivalent to the second unit, the third unit dealt with technical advising including goals, tasks, attitudes, settings, competences, and how to recruit and train future technical

advisers. The main method of technical advisers, the principle of minimum help, was trained and feed-backed by the trainers.

- The fourth unit combined and introduced team and technical advising as a tandem partnership, how advising is a collaboration between both advisers, the importance of communication between the advisers, and the kick-off to the project week.
- The last unit discussed further agents of support, such as the help desk and experts during the expert interviews, the project leadership, and supervision. The workshop ended with a general discussion crossing all topics and evaluation of the workshop itself.

A final reflection and evaluation with the participants indicated that they had learned how to adapt the German PPBL model structure at their university, how to manage a team, and how to implement the new teaching methods.

For future intercultural workshops, it is recommended based on our experiences to always remain in constant exchange with participants about their needs, experiences, and wishes to keep the material and topics relevant and suited for their world along with giving participants enough time to discuss, adapt, and implement learned knowledge. A critical success factor is using the pre-knowledge of participants to systematically build further practice and theory.

Generally constructive feedback is a significant tool for project teams to reflect upon their actions to constantly improve them. During the workshop, it was learned that the approach of giving and receiving feedback is unusual in Mongolian culture and tradition, even in everyday life communications. Nevertheless, the Mongolian staff were convinced that it would be fruitful for their students to learn and implement feedback during the study projects. The procedure needs to be adapted to be acceptable, culture-sensitive, and be valuable to Mongolian students. One needs to reflect on different feedback styles, traditions, and values whether it is German, American, or Mongolian and have an awareness of cultural differences. The focus should be placed on adapting feedback to concrete needs, resources, and capacities of the feedback receivers. Based on our experiences and discussions, we propose to gradually introduce and implement constructive feedback in these types of social environments by continuously scaffolding and successively deepening the intensity of feedback from day to day as follows in a one-week project course.

- On Monday, the teacher or team adviser should introduce the concept of the feedback approach on a meta-level and reflect upon and mediate unusual aspects with students along with introducing the rules of giving and receiving feedback. This should be followed by a demonstration of valuable resource-orientated feedback. Therefore, the team adviser might, at first, give solely positive reinforcements as feedback and exclusively at the team level (e.g. use of adequate working techniques applied by the team or collective team behaviors that could be seen as resources for effective teamwork). Thus, at the end of the day, students should have an idea of and the rules of feedback, and further be enabled to experience the reinforcing effect of receiving positive resource-oriented feedback.
- On Tuesday, the teacher or team adviser may repeat the philosophy and rules of constructive feedback while demonstrating the method themselves. Additionally, they should guide and encourage the students in groups of two to reflect upon their collaboration with the following questions: "Which techniques and team behaviors were supportive for teamwork and therefore should reinforced? What further ideas do you have to continuously improve your common teamwork?" It is suggested to use anonymous or semi-anonymous tools for this exercise. After collecting the responses, the team adviser should moderate a discussion over the named aspects and conclude

with additional regulating and resource-orientated feedback, including positive and negative aspects along with suggestions for improvement, and all should be supported with reasoning. The team adviser could also moderate a discussion with students about their experience with the feedback method.

- During the following days, the procedure should be continued with a successive increase in encouraging the students to expressing feedback to their own teamwork. Therefore, it depends on the students if the procedure should be more a partnership or use more (semi-) anonymous techniques. The aim of the scaffolding development should be to empower students to give feedback in a constructive, individual, and openly expressed way.
- Friday could end with a review and reflection on the entire week, guided by the team adviser. To aid understanding and to arrange feedback in a more tangible way for students, the procedure can be visualized each on a flipchart or on cards.

With this adapted approach of successively giving and receiving feedback in team advising, the procedure can be managed in a less direct way, and therefore, might be more accepted in social and cultural environments where participants are not used to this style of feedback. A focus on consequent positive reinforcement of team resources and constructive team behaviour is important to pave the way for a common basis of feedback. Further, team advisers need to not only introduce the practice of giving and receiving constructive feedback but also reiterate (many times) the underlying values and highlight the chances for collaboration within the team, learning and improvement, and the potential for personal growth and self-determination.

3.3 Step 3 – Mentoring by German staff

This past year, the Mongolian staff had the opportunity to practice, implement, and begin to adapt the German PPBL model at their university with mentoring from the German staff. Once more, as in the previous two years, a help desk was not utilized due to the small number of students, but expert interviews were with additional Mongolian academic staff participating and consulting on the student project solutions. Mongolian academic staff were the team advisers and introduced the key components of the PPBL model to the student teams with mentoring by the German staff along with technical advising. At the end of every day, a short reflection meeting was held between the Mongolian and German staff to discuss challenges and successes of that day and exchange ideas and thoughts for the next day. Overall, the project was run smoothly with good solutions presented by the student teams at the end of the project.

Additional informal reflection and discussion may be needed to help fully transition and transfer the model as challenges may arise in training new staff and involving upperclassman who took the project course as first year students.

4 LESSONS LEARNED, CHALLENGES, & RECOMMENDATIONS

Through this intercultural knowledge transfer of a PPBL model, we have learned to begin adapting the German PPBL model to a Mongolian university in collaboration between the German and Mongolian academic staff. Together, we have learned it is better to have more active technical advisers in teams and to have a modified feedback approach by team advisers. In consequence, this should empower the Mongolian university and staff to make the projects their own including materials and resources. Additionally, communication of different working styles at the beginning sets a basis for showing opportunities of possible adaptations of the concepts.

Challenges still remain in fully transferring and adapting the PPBL model. The major one is further training of team and technical advisers along with support staff to help run and organize the project courses and be self-sufficient.

From our experiences in an intercultural knowledge transfer, we recommend keeping the core part of the model similar between developed models but adapting as needed to be culture-specific such as the adapted, scaled, smooth fading-in practice of reflection and feedback. Developing local, “authentic problems” tasks that directly impact students is an easier way to get students excited and motivated about a project and for a university to adapt the model. For these knowledge transfers to successfully occur and for a new university to adapt and improve the model, there needs to be commitment and buy in from all stakeholders, including students, academic staff, and administration, by participation but minimally support these types of PPBL models. Any new adaptations to a system need time to be fully implemented; therefore, the adapted PPBL model will also need more time to show its full strengths.

Through critical reflection on our own practice in transferring the developed PPBL model, there is a need for further evaluation. We recommend collecting data and evaluating it (with appropriate permissions) to further quantify the quality and effectiveness of the adapted model along with identifying areas of improvement. It is also important to have future evaluations in the students’ mother tongue to reduce validity concerns over a potential language barrier.

In summary, international exchanges like these enables us to continuously improve and readjust the international and interdisciplinary PPBL model for culture-sensitive aspects, meaning not just handing over and teaching our PPBL model and tools to adapt it but also learning from our international colleagues and improving our project courses from this new knowledge we gain. Today’s needs for these types of transfers include eliciting formal organizational knowledge and tools and informal, more personal knowledge and experiences.

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